

When Truth Is Targeted: The Killing of Journalists and the Erasure of Memory in Palestine

Mahmoud S Elmasry | ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5839-5611>

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Executive Summary

This piece examines the systematic targeting of journalists in Gaza as a deliberate strategy of erasure, analysing its consequences for documentation, accountability, and the pursuit of justice. Drawing on incidents in August 2025 — including strikes on the Nasser Medical Complex and Al-Shifa Hospital — it situates the killing of over 190 journalists and media workers within a broader pattern of attacks on the infrastructure of truth. The piece argues that documentation in war is never neutral: it constitutes an act of survival and resistance, and its disruption through the targeting of journalists produces lasting gaps in evidence that undermine future accountability efforts. It further examines the role of artificial intelligence in compounding this erasure, through the automation of violence and the weaponisation of AI detection tools to discredit authentic evidence. The piece calls for strengthened documentation practices and international solidarity with frontline documenters as conditions for the possibility of justice.

The Systematic Targeting of Journalists in Gaza

On 25 August 2025, Israeli strikes on the Nasser Medical Complex in Khan Younis killed at least five journalists, including Associated Press freelancer Mariam Dagga, Al Jazeera journalist Mohammed Salama, Reuters cameraman Hussam al-Masri, and Reuters freelancer Moaz Abu Taha, along with medics and patients.¹ The attack was carried out in two consecutive strikes, the second of which struck journalists and first responders who had rushed to the scene of the first, a pattern suggesting deliberate intent rather than incidental harm.

This came only two weeks after an airstrike on the Al-Shifa Hospital killed four Al Jazeera journalists: reporter Anas al-Sharif, correspondent Mohammed Qreiqeh, and camera operators Ibrahim Zaher and Mohammed Noufal.² Al Jazeera denounced the attack as a

targeted assassination aimed at silencing the last remaining voices documenting events from inside Gaza.

More than 190 journalists and media workers have been killed in the Israel-Gaza war from 2023 to 2025, more press members than were killed worldwide in the prior three years combined.³ The Committee to Protect Journalists and other rights organisations have warned that these killings shatter the already fragile infrastructure of documentation on which accountability depends.

These killings are not isolated acts of violence but form part of a much broader pattern — a systematic attempt to dismantle the capacities to record, preserve, and expose violations. Such actions constitute not only violations of international law but, as human rights organisations have argued, amount to war crimes.⁴ Each life taken is also a severed connection to memory, evidence, and the possibility of justice. Silencing documentation is not collateral damage; it is a deliberate tactic.

Documentation as Resistance

Documentation in contexts of war and authoritarianism is never neutral. It is not simply news content, nor a stream of images for consumption. It is an act of survival and resistance, a way to preserve memory when official narratives deny or distort reality. Testimonies, videos, and photographs are not mere records of violence but instruments of justice — fragments of evidence that communities can hold onto in order to demand accountability. Journalists may be the most visible actors in this process, yet in their absence it is local communities and citizen documenters who take on this dangerous responsibility. Their recordings, often made at extraordinary personal risk, become part of a collective archive of truth. Without them, atrocities risk disappearing into silence, denied in the present and unprovable in the future.

The targeting of journalists therefore has consequences that extend far beyond the immediate loss of life. When a journalist is killed or disappeared, documentation is interrupted, testimonies are lost, and evidence that could have supported accountability is destroyed. Fear and uncertainty spread among others documenting — including citizen journalists — leading some to stop or restrict their work. This creates gaps in coverage that leave communities unseen and violations unrecorded. The result is a weakened body of evidence, making it harder to demonstrate patterns of abuse or pursue justice in the future. Killing journalists is

not only an attack on individuals; it is an attack on the broader human rights of entire communities struggling to put an end to injustice.

Artificial Intelligence and the Weaponisation of Doubt

Truth is also contested by technology. AI systems are being used to automate surveillance and the prosecution of violence in Gaza,⁵ but they are equally being deployed to undermine truth itself. AI-generated disinformation and the misuse of AI detection tools are eroding public trust in online information and creating new mechanisms to discredit authentic evidence. Documented evidence of crimes⁶ and real testimonies from people in Gaza appealing to global audiences⁷ have been falsely labelled as AI-generated, effectively erasing real experiences and undermining accountability.

Addressing this requires sustained attention to how provenance, detection, and safeguards against synthetic media are designed and governed.⁸ The challenge is not only to train documenters to preserve video evidence but to ensure that emerging AI tools are not weaponised to erase their testimonies. Protecting the integrity of documentation means grappling with both the physical violence directed at those who document and the epistemic violence directed at what they produce.

Conclusion

The killing of journalists in Gaza is a stark reminder of what is at stake when truth itself becomes a battlefield, and when the infrastructures of documentation are targeted precisely because of their power. What is recorded today will determine what can be remembered tomorrow, and whether justice can ever be pursued. Every preserved video, every archived testimony, and every trained documenter represents a refusal to allow violence to dictate silence. To continue documenting under such risk is not only an act of courage; it is an act of defiance against erasure.

Strengthening documentation practices and networks of solidarity is therefore not a peripheral concern for human rights advocacy, it is central to the possibility of accountability. Protecting documentation means keeping the possibility of justice alive.

Notes

¹ Associated Press (2025) 'Israeli strikes on Nasser Medical Complex kill at least five journalists', AP News, 25 August. Available at:

<https://apnews.com/article/mideast-wars-gaza-journalists-killed-5c33e999ee88effd89566a993b31d9cc> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

² Al Jazeera (2025) 'Al Jazeera journalist Anas al-Sharif killed in Israeli attack in Gaza City', Al Jazeera, 10 August. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2025/8/10/al-jazeera-journalist-anas-al-sharif-killed-in-israeli-attack-in-gaza-city> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

³ Committee to Protect Journalists (2025) 'Israel kills Al Jazeera journalists in targeted Gaza City airstrike', CPJ, August. Available at: <https://cpj.org/2025/08/israel-kills-al-jazeera-journalists-in-targeted-gaza-city-airstrike/> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

⁴ PEN America (2025) 'Israel's killing of journalists in Gaza could amount to a war crime', PEN America Press Release. Available at: <https://pen.org/press-release/israels-killing-of-journalists-in-gaza-could-amount-to-a-war-crime/> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

⁵ The Guardian (2025) 'Israel military AI surveillance', The Guardian, 6 March. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2025/mar/06/israel-military-ai-surveillance> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

⁶ Maiberg, E. (2025) 'AI image detectors are being used to discredit the real horrors of war', 404 Media. Available at: <https://www.404media.co/ai-images-detectors-are-being-used-to-discredit-the-real-horrors-of-war/> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

⁷ Gizmodo (2025) 'The rise of AI is making life even harder for real people in Gaza'. Available at: <https://gizmodo.com/the-rise-of-ai-is-making-life-even-harder-for-real-people-in-gaza-2000607395> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].

⁸ See: WITNESS (2025) 'Tomorrow's Great Digital Divide', WITNESS Blog, March. Available at: <https://blog.witness.org/2025/03/tomorrows-great-digital-divide/> [Accessed: 12 September 2025]; Hany, H. et al. (2025) 'Five real-world failures expose need for effective detection of AI-generated media', Tech Policy Press. Available at: <https://www.techpolicy.press/five-real-world-failures-expose-need-for-effective-detection-of-ai-generated-media/> [Accessed: 12 September 2025].